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EDUCATION FOR DIVERSITY: THE IMPLEMENTATION OF LAW 10.639/03 AND LAW 11.645/08 IN THE SCHOOL CURRICULUM

AUTHOR

Priscila dos Reis Pereira: Specialist in Special Education from the Federal University of Maranhão – BR, Pedagogue, Professor of Philosophy of Education at FACAM University.

Contact: priscilalimacorreitora@gmail.com | +55(98)98878-0900

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the implementation of Laws 10.639/03 and 11.645/08, which mandate the teaching of Afro-Brazilian, African, and Indigenous history and culture in Brazilian basic education. Based on bibliographic research, the advances, challenges, and obstacles faced in the process of incorporating these themes into the school curriculum were investigated. The results indicate that, despite legislative progress, difficulties persist related to insufficient teacher training, institutional resistance, and a lack of adequate teaching materials. The study highlights the importance of articulated public policies, community participation, and curricular transversality to consolidate an anti-racist and inclusive education. It concludes that the effective implementation of these laws is fundamental to promoting the recognition of cultural diversity and combating structural racism in the school environment, constituting an ethical and political commitment to building a more just and plural society.

Keywords: Anti-racist education. Law 10.639/03. Law 11.645/08. Afro-Brazilian history and culture. Ethnic-racial diversity. School curriculum. Teacher training.